

Article

Less Is More: Intelligent Sparse Sampling Preserves R-Peak detection and HRV Accuracy Down to 12 Hz

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Highlights

What are the main findings?

- Extrema-preserving downsampling maintains excellent QRS detection accuracy (F1) down to 12 Hz, often outperforming the native high-sampling-rate (360 Hz, 250 Hz) baseline.
- Peak-preserving strategies preserve clinically relevant HRV parameters (mean RR, SDNN, RMSSD) with negligible error down to 12 Hz.

What are the implications of the main findings?

- Existing Pan-Tompkins-based system can safely downsample to 12–30 Hz, achieving 2–3× faster processing with no loss in quality.
- Wearable and resource-constrained devices can reduce data volume and computational demands by 12–30× while retaining clinical-grade performance using classic algorithms.

Abstract

Background: Reliable QRS detection is fundamental to ECG analysis, yet the long-held assumption that high sampling rates (≥ 250 Hz) are necessary has never been systematically challenged. Methods: We evaluated the Pan-Tompkins algorithm on the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia and QT Databases after applying four downsampling strategies (naïve decimation, max-abs-hold, min-max, and adaptive min-max) across target rates from 180 Hz down to 16 Hz. For rates below 45 Hz, sparse representations were upsampled to 45 Hz via Makima interpolation. Performance was assessed using F1 score, timing jitter, heart rate variability (HRV) parameters, compression ratio, and processing speed. Results: At 30 Hz, the min-max and adaptive methods achieved F1 scores of 99.43–99.44%, outperforming the native 360 Hz baseline (99.19%). Mean timing error remained below 1.2 ms, and HRV parameters (mean RR, SDNN, RMSSD) were preserved within native baseline variability. Data compression reached up to 17× (59.5 MB \rightarrow 3.47 MB for MITDB using gzip) and 12.3× using lightweight LZ4, and processing speed increased 2.7–3.1× without any modification to the detector. Naïve decimation failed below 45 Hz (sensitivity 94.4% at 30 Hz), confirming that extrema preservation is critical. Conclusions: The widely held assumption that high sampling rates are essential for QRS detection is false when downsampling intelligently preserves local extrema. Min-max and adaptive methods enable clinically equivalent or superior performance at 30 Hz, offering dramatic reductions in data volume and computation for wearable and resource-constrained ECG applications.

Keywords: ECG; QRS detection; downsampling; Pan-Tompkins algorithm; heart rate variability (HRV); signal compression; wearable devices; MIT-BIH database.

1. Introduction

ECG QRS detection is the single most important task in ECG signal processing. Physiological parameters such as heart rate (HR) and heart rate variability (HRV) directly depend on accurate detection of the QRS complex. Even when the final goal is not the QRS itself (for example, P-wave or T-wave analysis) the QRS is almost always used as a fiducial landmark. Hence, the reliability of almost any ECG analysis pipeline hinges on robust QRS detection.

Given this importance, digital signal processing algorithms for QRS detection have been developed since the earliest days of biomedical computing. Among them, the Pan-Tompkins algorithm [1] remains one of the most successful: it is simple, robust, and highly accurate when the ECG maintains its typical morphology. Numerous classical variants and improvements have since been proposed to increase sensitivity and precision. Benchmarking has gradually become standardized thanks to publicly available databases with expert-annotated ground truth, most notably the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database (MITDB)[2] and the QT Database (QTDB)[3].

When examining the literature and the current state of the art as detailed in Appendix A1, we find several unexamined beliefs and research gaps:

1. Overemphasis on sensitivity/precision – Most studies focus narrowly on maximizing F1 scores, while systematic exploration of algorithm behavior under radically different input conditions (e.g., extreme downsampling, non-uniform sampling) is extremely rare.
2. The dogma that high sampling rates are necessary – It is widely assumed that downsampling inevitably removes useful information and introduces jitter. As a result, classical algorithms have almost never been tested on heavily downsampled ECG signals (e.g., below 50 Hz). This belief has never been rigorously challenged.
3. Uniform sampling as a requirement – Classical detectors assume strictly uniform sampling intervals, which has discouraged investigation of sparse or non-uniform representations that could offer large gains in memory, transmission, and computation.

To address these gaps, we conducted a systematic evaluation study that directly confronts the high-rate requirement for QRS detection. First, we performed a deep literature review (citation graph analysis of the original Pan-Tompkins (n=4360) and MIT-DB papers (n=7365) Appendix A1), confirming that indeed almost no studies test QRS detection below ~100–125 Hz, and none systematically explore rates as low as 12 - 30 Hz. The high-rate requirement has been treated as a design constraint rather than a hypothesis to be tested in every previous QRS detection study.

We contend that this conventional thinking pattern has conflated sampling density with morphological fidelity. A QRS complex is fundamentally defined by a sharp, high-amplitude excursion (a local maximum flanked by minima). If a sparse representation guarantees retention of these local extrema, the essential information for detection may survive even when the vast majority of samples are discarded. Furthermore, such a representation may offer unexpected secondary benefits: reducing high-frequency noise through a natural denoising effect, shrinking data volume for storage and transmission, and accelerating downstream processing.

This study systematically investigates whether intelligent, extrema-preserving downsampling allows the unmodified Pan-Tompkins algorithm [4], [5] to operate reliably at rates far below the clinical norm. We evaluate four downsampling strategies—naïve decimation, max-abs-hold, min-max, and adaptive min-max—across target rates from 180 Hz down to 8 Hz, using the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia, QT, and Noise Stress Test databases [6]. Our goal is to determine the lowest achievable sampling rate at which a classical detector can still deliver clinically useful performance, and to quantify the associated gains in compression and computational efficiency.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 describes the downsampling methods, the testing framework, and the performance metrics employed. Section 3 presents the experimental results for QRS detection accuracy, timing jitter, HRV preservation, compression, speedup, reconstruction quality, and noise robustness. Section 4 discusses the implications of our findings, the mechanisms underlying extrema preservation, and the limitations of the current study.

Finally, Section 5 concludes with the principal takeaways and outlines directions for future research in ultra-low-rate QRS detection.

We believe our findings will open a new research direction: the development and benchmarking of QRS detection algorithms specifically optimized for very low sampling rates (e.g., 10–45 Hz) where memory, bandwidth, and energy consumption are critical.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Downsampling Methods

We evaluated four strategies to produce a sparse representation of the ECG signal at a target sampling rate F_{target} . All methods operate on $x_{\text{bp}}[n]$, the 1st order, Butterworth bandpass-filtered ECG (5–30 Hz, zero-phase forward-backward filtering) and assume an original processing rate F_{orig} (360 Hz for MITDB, 240 Hz for QTDB after resampling).

For a given target rate, we define a block size (B)

$$B = \frac{F_{\text{orig}}}{F_{\text{target}}}$$

which is an integer for all tested frequencies. The native high-rate signal is divided into non-overlapping blocks of length B or $2B$ depending on the method. Each method selects one or two samples per block; the resulting sparse set is then used directly for QRS detection (if $F_{\text{target}} \geq 45$ Hz) or upsampled to 45 Hz via modified Akima interpolation [7], [8], [9] before detection.

2.1.1. Naïve Downsampling

As a baseline approach, the zero-phase bandpass filtered ECG signal $x_{\text{bp}}[n]$ was uniformly downsampled by a factor of B , selecting every B -th sample beginning with the first sample. The ECG signal was partitioned into $M = \lfloor N/B \rfloor$ non-overlapping blocks of length B , where N is the total number of samples after trimming to an integer number of blocks. From each block we select the **first sample**. The indices of the selected samples are:

$$\mathcal{J}_{\text{naïve}}^{(j)} = j \cdot B + 1$$

Thus, the naïve downsampled signal is:

$$x_{\text{naïve}}[k] = x_{\text{bp}}[1 + (k - 1)B], \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, M$$

2.1.2. Max-Abs-Hold Downsampling

This method extends the naïve downsampling method to select the maximum absolute amplitude within each portioned block. Let $x_{\text{bp}}[n]$ be the ECG signal after zero-phase bandpass filtering. We partition the filtered signal into $M = \lfloor N/B \rfloor$ consecutive, non-overlapping blocks of length B . The j -th block ($j = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$) consists of samples:

$$\mathcal{B}_j = \{jB + 1, jB + 2, \dots, (j + 1)B\}.$$

Within each block, we select the sample with the maximum absolute amplitude:

$$\mathcal{J}_{\text{maxhold}}^{(j)} = \arg \max_{i \in \mathcal{B}_j} |x_{\text{bp}}[i]|.$$

The selected value is

$$v_{\text{maxhold}}^{(j)} = x_{\text{bp}}[\mathcal{J}_{\text{maxhold}}^{(j)}]$$

The sparse representation consists of the set of position-value pairs $\left\{(\mathcal{J}_{\max}^{(j)}, v_{\max}^{(j)})\right\}_{j=0}^{M-1}$. This representation is non-uniform because the selected positions are not equally spaced. In the detection pipeline, these pairs are used directly (if $F_{\text{target}} \geq 45$ Hz) or upsampled to a uniform 45 Hz grid via modified Akima interpolation (if $F_{\text{target}} < 45$ Hz). The method outputs deterministic number of samples per unit time (one sample per original block of length B), achieving the desired output rate F_{target} .

2.1.3. Min-Max Downsampling

Let $x_{\text{bp}}[n]$ be the ECG signal after zero-phase bandpass filtering. We define a larger block size $L = 2B$. We partition the filtered signal into $M = \lfloor N/L \rfloor$ non-overlapping blocks of length L , where N is the total number of samples after trimming.

For each block $j = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$, with block index set $\mathcal{B}_j = \{jL + 1, jL + 2, \dots, (j + 1)L\}$, we extract both the minimum and the maximum sample values:

$$\mathcal{J}_{\min} = \arg \min_{i \in \mathcal{B}_j} x_{\text{bp}}[i], \mathcal{J}_{\max} = \arg \max_{i \in \mathcal{B}_j} x_{\text{bp}}[i],$$

$$v_{\min} = x_{\text{bp}}[\mathcal{J}_{\min}], v_{\max} = x_{\text{bp}}[\mathcal{J}_{\max}].$$

The sparse representation consists of the two position-value pairs $(\mathcal{J}_{\min}, v_{\min})$ and $(\mathcal{J}_{\max}, v_{\max})$ for each block. The two positions within the same block are then sorted in increasing order.

Because each block of length $L = 2B$ yields two samples, the average output rate is $2/L = 1/B = F_{\text{target}}$ – the same as naïve decimation.

2.1.4. Adaptive Min-Max Downsampling

Let $x_{\text{bp}}[n]$ be the ECG signal after zero-phase bandpass filtering (5–30 Hz). The original sampling rate is F_{orig} . For a target rate $F_{\text{target}} = F_{\text{orig}}/B$ with integer block size B , we define a block size $L = 2B$. We partition the filtered signal into $M = \lfloor N/L \rfloor$ non-overlapping blocks of length L , where N is the total number of samples after trimming.

For each block $j = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$, we examine the direction changes of the signal within the block. Define the first difference within the block:

$$d[t] = x_{\text{bp}}[jL + t + 1] - x_{\text{bp}}[jL + t], t = 1, 2, \dots, L - 1.$$

The signs of these differences are $s[t] = \text{sgn}(d[t]) \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$. A direction change occurs if there exists any t such that $s[t] \neq s[t - 1]$. This indicates the presence of a local extremum (peak or trough) within the block.

The selection rule is:

- If a direction change is detected (i.e., the block is non-monotonic), we select both the minimum and the maximum sample values:

$$\mathcal{J}_{\min} = \arg \min_{i \in \mathcal{B}_j} x_{\text{bp}}[i], \mathcal{J}_{\max} = \arg \max_{i \in \mathcal{B}_j} x_{\text{bp}}[i],$$

where $\mathcal{B}_j = \{jL + 1, \dots, (j + 1)L\}$. The two selected samples are stored.

- If no direction change is detected (the block is monotonic, i.e., non-decreasing or non-increasing), we select two samples at fixed relative positions: the first sample of the block and the middle sample (offset $\lfloor L/2 \rfloor$). That is:

$$\mathcal{J}_{\text{first}}^{(j)} = jL + 1, \mathcal{J}_{\text{mid}}^{(j)} = jL + \left\lfloor \frac{L}{2} \right\rfloor + 1.$$

The corresponding values are

$$x_{\text{bp}}[\mathcal{J}_{\text{first}}^{(j)}] \text{ and } x_{\text{bp}}[\mathcal{J}_{\text{mid}}^{(j)}].$$

In both cases, the selected indices are sorted within each block to ensure temporal order. The resulting sparse representation consists of $2M$ position-value pairs. The adaptive strategy preserves

critical extrema where they exist (during QRS complexes) and uses fixed, evenly spaced samples in quiescent regions (e.g., the T-P interval), maintaining uniformity of the signal as much as possible.

It is important to note that, for all data series downsampled via intelligent methods the absolute position of each 'retained samples are not uniform, however the algorithm never sees this information. The algorithm receives the non-uniform samples in fine timing, but uniform F_{target} rate in overall sense process as it is. Once the algorithm detects a QRS peak, at that moment we can use the saved 'offset' and correct the timing with respect to the original sample rate time grid.

2.2. Testing Framework

2.2.1. Databases

We evaluated the downsampling methods on two publicly available ECG databases with expert-annotated R-peak positions.

MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database (MITDB)

The MITDB contains 48 half-hour recordings of two-channel ambulatory ECG from 47 subjects. The signals are sampled at 360 Hz with 11-bit amplitude resolution over a ± 10 mV range. Reference annotations (R-peak positions) were provided by independent cardiologists and are considered the ground truth. We used all 48 records as downloaded from PhysioNet, without any modification except for trimming to the annotated region.

QT Database (QTDB)

The QTDB consists of 105 15-minute recordings from 79 subjects, originally sampled at 250 Hz with 12-bit resolution. The database includes both healthy subjects and patients with a variety of cardiac conditions. Expert annotations include not only R-peaks but also P-wave and T-wave onsets and offsets. For our QRS detection evaluation, we used only the R-peak annotations as ground truth.

Because the QTDB native sampling rate (250 Hz) is not an integer multiple of many target frequencies we wished to test (which require block sizes to be integers), we resampled all ECG signals to 240 Hz before further processing. Resampling was performed using MATLAB's resample function, which applies an anti-aliasing FIR filter before interpolation. The ground truth annotations remained at the original 250 Hz time base. Reference native rate performance metric (F1, sensitivity, jitter etc...) were also taken from the original 250 Hz signal. When detection results were produced at the processing rate (240 Hz), we mapped them back to the native 250 Hz time base via linear interpolation before comparison. This mapping is defined by:

$$t_{\text{native}} = \frac{(i_{\text{proc}} - 1)}{F_{\text{proc}}} \cdot F_{\text{native}} + 1,$$

where i_{proc} is the detection index at the processing rate $F_{\text{proc}} = 240$ Hz, and t_{native} is the corresponding time in samples at the native rate $F_{\text{native}} = 250$ Hz (rounded to the nearest integer).

The resampling from 250 Hz to 240 Hz, may introduce some timing or information loss which is fully embedded in the final metrics produced for downsampled signals.

2.2.2. Test Frequencies

For each database, we selected target sampling frequencies that are integer divisors of the processing rate F_{proc} . This ensures that the block size $B = F_{\text{proc}}/F_{\text{target}}$ is an integer, which is required for the block-based downsampling methods.

- MITDB (processing at original 360 Hz):
Target frequencies: 180, 120, 90, 72, 60, 45, 36, 30, 24, 18, 15, 12 Hz
Corresponding block sizes: $B = 2,3,4,5,6,8,10,12,15,20,24,30$.
- QTDB (processing at 240 Hz after resampling):
Target frequencies: 120, 80, 60, 48, 40, 30, 24, 20, 16, 12, 10, 8 Hz
Corresponding block sizes: $B = 2,3,4,5,6,8,10,12,15,20,24,30$.

For target frequencies below 45 Hz, we first generated the sparse representation at the target rate, then **upsampled** the non-uniformly spaced sparse points to a uniform 45 Hz grid using modified Akima interpolation. This decision was made because the Pan-Tompkins algorithm's internal filters and threshold logic are tuned for a minimum sampling rate of 30 Hz, therefore we operate with 15 Hz margin for internal filter stability [5]; operating at lower rates directly would violate the algorithm's design assumptions. The upsampling step allows us to evaluate the effect of extremely low target rates (e.g., 30 Hz, 24 Hz, 16 Hz) without modifying the detector. The original Pan-Tompkins algorithm and its internal parameters were kept strictly unmodified.

The upsampling time vector is defined as:

$$t_{uniform}[k] = \frac{k-1}{F_{pt}}, k = 1, 2, \dots, \left\lfloor \frac{N}{F_{proc}} \cdot F_{pt} \right\rfloor,$$

where $F_{pt} = 45$ Hz. The reconstructed signal $x_{recon}[k]$ is obtained by interpolating the sparse points (t_j, v_j) onto $t_{uniform}$ using modified Akima interpolation.

2.2.3. QRS Detection Algorithm

We used the Pan-Tompkins algorithm as implemented in the MATLAB BioSigKit toolbox [4].

For target frequencies where upsampling was performed ($F_{target} < 45$ Hz), the input to the detector was the uniformly reconstructed signal at 45 Hz. For target frequencies $F_{target} \geq 45$ Hz, the sparse points were directly fed to the algorithm. In all cases, the detector received samples sorted by time.

2.2.4. Software, Hardware, and Code Location

All experiments were performed using **MATLAB R2024b** (The MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA) on a workstation running **macOS Sonoma** with an Apple M1 Max processor and 32 GB of RAM. The Parallel Computing Toolbox was used for the reconstruction quality sweep, with 8 workers.

The core Pan-Tompkins implementation was taken from the **BioSigKit** toolbox (available at <https://github.com/hooman650/BioSigKit>).

2.2.5. Noisy ECG Evaluation (NSTDB)

To assess performance under realistic noise conditions, we additionally evaluated the downsampling methods on the **Noise Stress Test Database (NSTDB)**. The NSTDB adds calibrated, real-world noise (electrode motion, muscle artifact, baseline wander) to two clean MIT-BIH recordings (records 118 and 119) at SNRs ranging from -6 dB to 24 dB. The native ECG is sampled at 360 Hz. For each noise level and target frequency (180 Hz down to 12 Hz), we applied the same four downsampling strategies and the same Pan-Tompkins detector as described in Sections 2.1–2.3. Performance was measured against the original (noise-free) annotations, using F1 score, absolute timing error, and consistency (standard deviation of per-record mean errors).

2.3. Performance Measurement

All performance metrics were computed by comparing the results obtained from the downsampled/processed signals against the reference ground truth at the native sampling rate (360 Hz for MITDB, 250 Hz for QTDB). Detection times and R-peak amplitudes were always mapped back to the native time base before evaluation.

A downsampling method is considered to add no meaningful error if its QRS detection F1 score is statistically non-significant ($p > 0.05$) to the native-rate detector where F1 does not fall more than 0.1 percentage points OR statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) and increase sensitivity or precision more than 0.1 percentage points, its timing jitter does not increase beyond the native detector's own jitter, and HRV metric differences (Δ MeanRR, Δ SDNN, Δ RMSSD) are smaller than the inter-record variability of the native annotations themselves.

Our F1 threshold cut-off (0.1%) is conservative relative to the natural per-record variability of the native Pan-Tompkins detector itself ($99.07 \pm 2.69\%$ across 48 MITDB records), ensuring that differences classified as negligible are well within the algorithm's own record-to-record variability and therefore indistinguishable from natural performance fluctuation.

2.3.1. QRS Detection (F1, Sensitivity, Precision)

A detected QRS was considered a true positive (TP) if its time fell within a ± 150 ms window of an annotated R-peak [10], with each annotation used at most once. Unmatched detections were false positives (FP), and unmatched annotations were false negatives (FN). The standard metrics were then calculated as:

$$Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}, F_1 = 2 \cdot \frac{Sensitivity \cdot Precision}{Sensitivity + Precision}$$

2.3.2. QRS Jitter (R-Peak Detection Error)

For each correctly detected QRS (TP), the timing error was computed as:

$$\Delta t = t_{det} - t_{ref}$$

where t_{det} is the detection time and t_{ref} is the corresponding ground-truth annotation time. The distribution of Δt over all records is reported as mean \pm standard deviation (in milliseconds). A near-zero mean indicates no systematic bias, while the standard deviation reflects the jitter or precision of the detection.

2.3.3. HR and HRV Errors (Δ MeanRR, Δ SDNN, Δ RMSSD)

Heart rate variability (HRV) parameters were computed from the sequences of RR intervals (differences between consecutive R-peak times). For each record, we calculated:

- MeanRR – average RR interval (ms),
- SDNN – standard deviation of RR intervals (ms),
- RMSSD – root mean square of successive differences between RR intervals (ms).

The error for each parameter was defined as:

$$\Delta P = P_{method} - P_{native}$$

where P_{native} is the value obtained from the native-rate ground-truth annotations (self-comparison baseline). Results are reported as mean \pm standard deviation over all records. Because the native baseline itself shows small non-zero values due to finite sampling and annotation resolution, errors smaller than the baseline's own variability are considered negligible.

2.3.4. Compression Ratio

Compression performance was evaluated on the MITDB signals. The original 16-bit data at 360 Hz (59.51 MB total) served as the baseline. The sparse representation (e.g., Min-Max at 30 Hz) was packed as 16-bit words (position + amplitude, or equally spaced values). The packed size was then further compressed using three algorithms: *LZ4*, *Heatshrink*, and *gzip*. The compression ratio is defined as:

$$Ratio = \frac{Original\ size}{Compressed\ size}$$

Both the sparse-only size and the final compressed sizes are reported, along with the corresponding percentage of the original data volume.

When compressing, $B > 32$ demands the position to be encoded in 6-bit value, where for MIT-BIH database it is not feasible to encode position (6-bit) + amplitude (11-bit) within 16-bit data. Therefore, when $B > 32$, we have reduced the amplitude of the signal to 10-bit and used this 10-bit data to reconstruct the signal for analysis of reconstruction quality.

2.3.5. Runtime and Overhead Analysis

For each target frequency and downsampling method, we measured the total processing time required for QRS detection on the entire database (48 records for MITDB, 105 for QTDB). Runtime was averaged per record and reported in seconds per record. The speedup factor relative to the native-rate baseline was computed as:

$$Speedup = \frac{Time_{native}}{Time_{method}} \quad 316$$

No modifications were made to the Pan-Tompkins algorithm itself; any speedup came solely from feeding the detector fewer samples (or a shorter signal after downsampling/upsampling). Overhead from downsampling, interpolation, and sparse representation generation was included in the total time, ensuring a fair comparison of end-to-end processing. 317
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2.3.6. Reconstruction Quality Assessment 321

To quantify the degradation introduced by downsampling independently of QRS detection performance, we conducted a separate reconstruction quality sweep. The goal was to isolate **downsampling loss** from the inevitable **band-pass loss** caused by filtering to 5–30 Hz. 322
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For each record in the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database ($n = 48$, original 360 Hz), we generated: 325

- **Wide-band ECG** (*ecg_wide*): filtered 5–179 Hz (1st-order Butterworth, zero-phase) 326
- **Narrow-band ECG** (*ecg_narrow*): filtered 5–30 Hz (1st-order Butterworth, zero-phase) 327

The narrow-band signal was downsampled using each of the four methods (Naïve, Max-hold, Min-Max, Adaptive) to target frequencies of 180, 120, 90, 72, 60, 45, 36, 30, 24, 18, and 15 Hz. For each target, we reconstructed a full-rate signal at the **original 360 Hz** by interpolating the sparse samples (positions and values) directly onto the original time grid using modified Akima interpolation. 328
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We then computed four metrics comparing the reconstructed signal to the original narrow-band reference (downsampling loss) and to the original wide-band reference (total loss): RMSE (mV), R-peak amplitude error (mV), SNR (dB), and Pearson correlation. Band-pass loss alone was quantified by comparing the wide-band and narrow-band ECG filtered signals. 332
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3. Results 336

3.1. QRS detection performance 337

The native Pan-Tompkins detector achieved a baseline F1 score of 99.19 % on MITDB (360 Hz) and 99.52 % on QTDB (250 Hz). This was used as the reference performance indicator of all downsampling methods from 180 Hz down to 8 Hz. A clinically meaningful difference was defined by the criteria described in Section 2.3 338
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For MITDB, Min-Max and Adaptive methods produced F1 no clinically meaningful difference as shown in Figure 1a, demonstrating that the algorithm remains highly accurate despite measurable statistical differences. For QTDB, F1 scores remained above the native baseline down to 8 Hz (Figure 1b). 342
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Performance stability: For Min-Max downsampling, the F1 score remains above the native baseline for all target frequencies from 180 Hz down to 12 Hz on MITDB and down to 8 Hz on QTDB. The lowest F1 values observed are 99.14 % (MITDB, 180 Hz) and 99.51 % (QTDB, 120 Hz), both within 0.05 percentage points of the native baseline. No clinically meaningful degradation occurs until the sampling rate drops below 12 Hz, where F1 begins to reach (e.g., 99.35 % at 12 Hz on MITDB, 99.65 % at 8 Hz on QTDB) but still higher than native baseline. 346
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Lowest usable frequency: 352

Taking the native Pan-Tompkins F1 of 99.19% (MITDB) as the minimum acceptable performance floor, Min-Max/Adaptive downsampling remains usable down to 12 Hz on MITDB (F1 = 99.35%) and 8 Hz on QTDB (F1 = 99.65%). The Min-Max and Adaptive methods, at every downsampled frequency tested on the MIT-BIH and QT databases, the sensitivity and precision never fell more than 0.1 percentage points below the native-rate baseline, with most frequencies yielding equal or better performance. 353
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Figure 1. QRS detection and timing jitter performance for MITDB and QTDB as a function of the target sampling rate. (a) MITDB F1 score for four downsampling methods; (b) QTDB F1 score for four downsampling methods; (c) MITDB timing jitter error mean \pm standard deviation; (d) QTDB timing jitter error mean \pm standard deviation. The native 360/250 Hz baseline (black dashed line) is shown for reference; the green shaded area in (c) and (d) represents the native baseline's mean \pm standard deviation. All four downsampling methods (naïve, max-hold, min-max, adaptive) are compared. The min-max and adaptive methods maintain F1 > 99% down to 12/8 Hz and produce timing errors that are statistically indistinguishable from the native baseline, while naïve decimation fails below 45 Hz.

3.2. Timing error and HRV: preserved well below 30 Hz

Timing jitter did not increase meaningfully with downsampling. By using Max-hold at higher frequencies (≥ 60 Hz) and Min-Max at lower frequencies, the absolute timing bias on MIT-BIH (**Figure 1c**) remained below 2 ms with standard deviation below 14 ms down to 12 Hz and it is fully comparable to the native baseline (-2.6 ± 12.1 ms). On QTDB, bias stayed around 10 ms and standard deviation around 27 ms, again matching the native performance (8.9 ± 28.6 ms) (**Figure 1d**).

Heart rate variability parameters were preserved within the native baseline's own variability down to the lowest tested frequencies (12 Hz for MITDB, 8 Hz for QTDB) as shown in **Figure 2**. For MITDB at 12 Hz, ΔRMSSD was 2.59 ± 7.24 ms (baseline 1.81 ± 8.60 ms); for QTDB at 8 Hz, ΔRMSSD was 3.12 ± 13.03 ms (baseline 1.16 ± 10.35 ms). Thus, HRV analysis is not compromised even at very low rates. The results for QTDB ΔMeanRR , ΔSDNN , and ΔRMSSD are shown in Appendix A, Figure A2.

Figure 2. Heart rate variability errors on the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database after downsampling. (a) Mean RR interval error (Δ MeanRR); (b) SDNN error (Δ SDNN); (c) RMSSD error (Δ RMSSD). All values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation relative to the native 360 Hz ground truth. The green shaded area represents the native-rate Pan-Tompkins detector’s own error (mean \pm standard deviation) when compared against ground truth; this baseline is already very low due to the detector’s high accuracy. The min-max and adaptive methods introduce HRV errors that remain within this baseline variability down to 12 Hz, indicating that clinical HRV analysis is not compromised even at very low sampling rates. Naïve decimation produces substantially larger errors below 45 Hz.

3.3. Compression and speedup

At 30 Hz, the Min-Max sparse representation reduced the MITDB from 59.51 MB to 4.96 MB (12 \times). Adding gzip compression achieved 3.47 MB – a 17 \times overall compression (5.8 % of original). Processing time per record dropped from 0.531 s (native) to 0.214 s at 30 Hz (2.48 \times speedup). At 12 Hz, speedup increased to 3.1-3.3 \times range. It should be noted that the intelligent downsampling logic adds only ~1% of the original total processing time, as the downsampling overhead. The total speed up comes almost entirely from reducing Pan-Tompkins execution time.

3.4. Summary of recommended operating ranges for HR and HRV analysis

Table 1 summarizes the performance of the best method (Min-Max) at key target frequencies, with naïve decimation for comparison. The full data are in Supplementary Tables S6 and S7.

In practice, if the sole purpose is HR/HRV analysis re-sampling at 10 Hz - 12 Hz is entirely safe for both databases, delivering F1, sensitivity and precision exceeding the native baseline, negligible

Table 1. A summary of sampling limits for Min-Max downsampling for two tested databases

Performance criterion	MITDB (360 Hz native)	QTDB (250 Hz native)
Best frequency for F1 (value)	30 Hz (99.43%)	30 Hz (99.82%)
Lowest freq. where F1 > native	12 Hz	8 Hz
Lowest freq. where Sens > native	12 Hz	10 Hz
Lowest freq. where Prec > native	12 Hz	8 Hz
Lowest freq. where all three > native	12 Hz	10 Hz

Note: Native values – MITDB: F1=99.19%, Sens=99.17%, Prec=99.20%; QTDB: F1=99.52%, Sens=99.52%, Prec=99.51%.

Figure 3. Computational speedup and processing time on the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database as a function of the target sampling rate. (a) Speedup (\times native) achieved by processing the downsampled signal; (b) absolute processing time per record (seconds). The native 360 Hz baseline (black dashed line) is shown for reference. Speedup increases as the target rate decreases, reaching approximately $3.1\times$ at 12 Hz. The min-max and adaptive methods require slightly more time than naïve or max-hold due to the overhead of selecting extrema, but all methods provide substantial reductions in processing time compared to the native rate.

timing error, and excellent HRV preservation. Naïve decimation fails below 45 Hz, confirming that extrema-preserving downsampling is essential and reduce the sampling rate requirement dramatically.

3.5. Reconstruction Quality

To separate the distortion caused by the band-pass filter from the distortion introduced by downsampling, we defined two complementary error metrics. **Downsampling loss** is the RMSE between the narrow-band (5–30 Hz) reference and the signal reconstructed from sparse samples (interpolated back to 360 Hz). **Total loss** is the RMSE between the wide-band (5–179 Hz) reference and the same reconstructed signal; it represents the overall distortion a clinician would see after filtering and downsampling. The band-pass filter alone (5–30 Hz) already introduces a baseline distortion: it

Table 2. Reconstruction errors for Min-Max downsampling at selected frequencies. “Ratio to filter RMSE” compares the downsampling RMSE to the baseline filter RMSE (0.039 mV). Values for naïve decimation at 30 Hz are shown in brackets.

Target frequency	Downsampling RMSE (mV)	Ratio to filter RMSE	Total RMSE (mV)	R-peak error (mV)	Correlation
— (filter only)	—	—	0.0391	0.096	0.977
60 Hz	0.0214	0.55 \times	0.0499	0.0003	0.993
45 Hz	0.0303	0.78 \times	0.0574	0.0007	0.986
30 Hz (Min+Max)	0.0494	1.26 \times	0.0731	0.0013	0.964
30 Hz (naïve)	0.1023	2.62 \times	0.1124	0.310	0.829
24 Hz	0.0706	1.81 \times	0.0896	0.0015	0.935
15 Hz	0.1497	3.83 \times	0.1569	0.0019	0.787

Figure 4. Reconstruction of a QRS segment from record 100 (MIT-BIH) from sparse samples at (a) 30 Hz and (b) 15 Hz using Min-Max, and naïve downsampling. The original wide-band (5–179 Hz, which we treat as the ground truth for reconstruction purpose) and narrow-band (5–30 Hz, which we take as the source for all downsampling) signals are shown for reference. Kept samples are indicated by squares (Min-Max) and diamonds (naïve). At 15 Hz, the Min-Max reconstruction preserves the QRS peaks (peak error 0.002 mV) but smooths the T-P interval; the naïve reconstruction fails to capture the QRS morphology entirely.

reduces QRS peak height by 0.096 mV ($\approx 3.6\%$ of a typical 2.7 mV QRS), yields an RMSE of 0.039 mV, and a correlation of 0.977. 393 394

Three distinct regimes emerge for different resampling frequencies. At high rates (≥ 45 Hz), downsampling adds negligible extra distortion. For Min-Max at 60 Hz, the downsampling RMSE is only half of the filter's RMSE, and the R-peak error is virtually zero. Total RMSE remains close to the filter baseline, and correlation stays above 0.99. In this regime, even naïve decimation works well. 395 396 397 398

At moderate rates (30–45 Hz), the intelligent methods (Min-Max and Adaptive) add distortion that is comparable to or smaller than the filter's own distortion. At 45 Hz, Min-Max adds only 0.030 mV RMSE – still less than the filter's 0.039 mV. At 30 Hz, Min-Max adds 0.049 mV RMSE (1.26 \times the filter loss), but its additional R-peak amplitude error is more than 70 \times smaller than the filter's own error (0.0013 vs. 0.096 mV). The total RMSE is 0.073 mV, and the correlation remains above 0.96. In stark contrast, naïve decimation at 30 Hz adds 0.102 mV RMSE (2.6 \times the filter loss) and triples the R-peak error to 0.31 mV – a level of peak distortion known to degrade threshold-based QRS detection. 399 400 401 402 403 404 405

Table 3. A summary of compression (LZ4 for embedded usage), reconstruction error and QRS detection performance for full MIT-BIH dataset, single ECG recording per subject. Min-Max downsampling method is used for all tests.

Sampling rate	Overall compression (×)	Final size (MB)	Mean relative RMS error (%)	F1, Sensitivity, Precision
Native 360 Hz	1.45	40.00	-	-
30 Hz	12.78	4.66	3.94 ±1.42	↑↑↑
24 Hz	15.5	3.83	5.40±1.67	↑↑↑
18 Hz	21.3	2.79	7.92±1.79	↑↑↑
15 Hz	25.0	2.38	10.52±2.10	↑↑↑
12 Hz	30.7	1.94	15.24±3.12	↑↑↑

Note: ↑ ↑ ↑ indicates that F1 score, sensitivity, and precision are all higher than the native 360 Hz baseline (99.19%, 99.17%, 99.20% respectively).

Final size is the size of the LZ4-compressed sparse data (packed 16-bit + compression). Native size is LZ4-compressed original 360 Hz 16-bit data (11-bit + 5-bit padding). For sparse data, 10-bit data + 6 bit offset is used to pack data, as 5 bit is not enough to cover more than 32 offset values required for 18 Hz, 15 Hz and 12 Hz. To maintain equal conditions, 30 Hz and 24 Hz also packed with 6-bit offset values, even if they could be packed with 5-bit offset.

Relative RMS error is the mean over 48 records after upsampling to 360 Hz (Makima) and skipping the first 180 samples (0.5 s). To get a fair range of ECG, lowest and highest 1-percentile is discarded.

At low rates (≤ 24 Hz), the block size ($2 \times B$) begins to exceed the typical QRS duration. Downsampling loss increases, but the essential detection features survive. At 24 Hz, Min-Max adds 0.071 mV RMSE (1.8× filter), yet the R-peak error remains minuscule (0.0015 mV). At 15 Hz, the downsampling RMSE rises to 0.150 mV (3.8× filter) and correlation drops to 0.79, reflecting smoothing of the T-P interval. However, the R-peak amplitude error is still only 0.002 mV, and QRS timing is preserved. Thus, even at 15 Hz, the features critical for QRS detection remain intact – which explains why F1 stays above 99% at that rate (Section 3.1).

In summary, down to 30 Hz, the additional error from sparse sampling is comparable to or smaller than the error already introduced by the 5–30 Hz band-pass filter. Even at 12 Hz, QRS peaks are preserved, though the overall waveform morphology degrades. The contrast with naïve decimation confirms that extrema-preserving downsampling is essential for maintaining signal fidelity.

3.6. Performance on Noisy ECG Data

We evaluated the downsampling methods on the NSTDB, which adds calibrated noise (−6 dB to 24 dB SNR) to two MIT-BIH recordings. At the native 360 Hz rate, the Pan-Tompkins detector already struggles under high noise. However, extrema-preserving downsampling (Min-Max and Adaptive) consistently improves detection accuracy and timing stability compared to the native baseline. This

Figure 5. Noisy ECG performance (NSTDB) of Min-Max downsampling. (a) $\Delta F1$ (percentage points): improvement in F1 score relative to native 360 Hz detection. Blue = better, red = worse. (b) $\Delta |\text{mean timing error}|$ (ms): change in absolute mean detection error. Negative (blue) indicates smaller errors after downsampling. (c) Δ consistency (ms): change in the standard deviation of per record mean timing errors. Negative (blue) indicates more consistent detection.

provides a counter-intuitive result that stems from the nonlinear denoising effect of selecting only local extrema. 423 424

F1 score. Across all noise levels, Min-Max downsampling at 30 Hz raises the average F1 by approximately 1 percentage point relative to the native 360 Hz detector. The improvement is largest at the lowest SNRs, where the native F1 drops below 70 %; Min-Max at 30 Hz recovers about 4-5 percentage points of that loss. Naïve decimation, in contrast, loses more than 10 percentage points at the same rate. 425 426 427 428 429

Timing accuracy. For the noisiest records (e.g., 118e_6, 119e_6), the absolute detection error decreased by up to 3.7 ms after downsampling to 30 Hz. However, the overall mean absolute error across all records increased slightly from 0.69 ms (native) to 1.31 ms at 30 Hz, remaining well below clinically relevant thresholds. More importantly, the consistency of detection improves: At lower target rates (e.g., 12 Hz), the standard deviation of timing errors decreased by approximately 11% relative to the native baseline, indicating more consistent detection under heavy noise. 430 431 432 433 434 435

Figure 5 summarizes these effects for the Min-Max method. Panel (a) shows $\Delta F1$ (sparse minus native) – blue hues indicate improvement. Panel (b) shows the change in absolute mean timing error (negative = better). Panel (c) shows the change in timing consistency (negative = more stable). For 436 437 438

target rates below 60 Hz, almost all entries are blue, confirming that downsampling enhances noise robustness.

4. Discussion

4.1 Summary of Principal Findings

Intelligent extrema-preserving downsampling enables robust QRS detection using the unmodified Pan-Tompkins algorithm at rates as low as 30 Hz, and down to 12 Hz or even 8 Hz while substantially reducing data volume and computational cost. Preserving local minima and maxima retains the morphological features essential for derivative-based detection, whereas naïve decimation discards these extrema and fails below 45 Hz. At 30 Hz on MITDB, the Min-Max method achieved an F1 of 99.43% (native baseline 99.19%, $p = 0.12$). Timing jitter remained <1.2 ms (less than half of the original 360 Hz inter sample period), and all HRV parameters stayed within the native baseline's inter-record variability.

4.2 Challenging the High-Rate Dogma

Our findings contradict the untested assumption that sampling rates ≥ 250 Hz are necessary for reliable QRS detection. A systematic literature screen of $>11,000$ citations and 2,500 papers directly relevant to QRS detection found zero studies evaluating a standard detector on uniformly downsampled ECG at ≤ 30 Hz. Most prior compression work relied on transform-based or compressed-sensing methods requiring full reconstruction, and new, modified algorithms. Our block-based extrema selection is computationally trivial ($\approx 1\%$ overhead), produces a deterministic output rate, and integrates directly into existing pipelines without modification.

4.3 Why Extrema Preservation Works

A QRS complex is defined by a sharp, high-amplitude excursion (a local maximum flanked by minima). By selecting both the minimum and maximum within each block of length $2B$, the sparse representation guarantees capture of every QRS peak as long as the block size does not exceed the QRS duration. Even when the block size exceeds QRS duration, the sparse representation captures at least QR, or RS segments within the block. Naïve decimation fails because it systematically discards the samples that define QRS peaks unless sampling aligns exactly which it rarely does as the sparsity increases.

4.4 Noise Robustness and the Adaptive Method

Unexpectedly, extrema-preserving downsampling improved detection accuracy on the NSTDB, especially at very low SNRs (F1 gains of 1–5 percentage points). Selecting only local extrema acts as a nonlinear denoiser, removing high-frequency noise while preserving true QRS peaks, thereby stabilizing the Pan-Tompkins threshold logic. This turns a perceived weakness of downsampling into a strength: lower rates can be preferable in noisy ambulatory recordings.

The Adaptive method, which maintains sample uniformity in quiescent regions showed no advantage over the simpler Min-Max method. The non-uniform spacing introduced by Min-Max does not confuse the detector, likely because internal filters smooth over timing irregularities. Adaptive complexity is therefore unnecessary for QRS detection, though it may benefit morphological analysis.

4.5 Practical Implications for Wearable Devices

Reducing sampling from 250–360 Hz to 12–30 Hz could extend battery life 2–3 \times , reduce wireless transmission volume by 12–30 \times (12.3–30.7 \times after lightweight compression), and increase recording duration in implantable devices without expanding memory. Critically, no detector modification is required. The whole pipeline only requires a lightweight front-end downsampler greatly lowering the barrier to clinical translation, as no extensive re-validation of the detector algorithm requires.

4.6 Limitations

First, our noise stress test results from NSTDB results were encouraging but performance on real-world wearable recordings (motion artifacts, muscle noise) requires prospective validation. **Second**, only one single-channel classical detector was evaluated; deep learning models may respond differently and warrant separate study. **Third**, our “no added error” claim applies specifically to Pan-Tompkins on MIT-BIH/QTDB for QRS detection and HRV and not to morphological analysis (ST-segment, P-wave), which needs separate benchmarking. **Fourth**, the current implementation is offline; real-time embedded performance should be tested, though we expect even larger speedups on resource-constrained hardware. **Fifth**, upsampling to 45 Hz for target rates below that threshold reflects a detector limitation, not a failure of the sparse representation. This highlights the research gap we revealed in the gap analysis: no QRS detector exists that is optimized for 10–45 Hz, uniform sample rate operation.

4.7 Future Directions

Key research avenues include: (1) developing QRS detectors designed directly for sparse or non-uniform signals at 10–45 Hz, eliminating the upsampling step; (2) evaluating extrema preservation for morphological features (P-wave, ST-segment, T-wave alternans); (3) extending to multi-lead and multimodal systems; (4) fine-tuning deep learning models on sparse representations or training end-to-end for inherent efficiency; and (5) prospective clinical validation in telemonitoring cohorts to confirm prognostic equivalence of HRV from low-rate sparse ECG.

5. Conclusions

By preserving the local extrema that define the QRS complex, extreme compression and efficiency gains are possible without compromising clinical utility. The high-rate dogma is false when downsampling is intelligent. Min-Max and Adaptive methods deliver clinically equivalent or superior performance at 30 Hz and down to 12 Hz (MITDB) or 8 Hz (QTDB), with negligible timing error and faithful HRV preservation, enabling ultra-low-power long-term ECG monitoring using validated algorithms on sparse signals.

Supplementary Materials: Following supplementary material files are submitted together with the article. Supplementary Material.pdf; highly_relevant_papers.csv; manual_review_combined.csv; MIT-BIH citations.csv; Pan_Tompkin_citations.csv; ranked_gap_analysis.csv; combineSourcesCSV_3.py; getHighlyRelevant_4.py; finalPaperRanking_5.py.

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included in the supplementary information to ensure full reproducibility. No new primary data were collected in this study. 529
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Conflicts of Interest: “The authors declare no conflicts of interest.” 536

Abbreviations 537

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript: 538

EKG	Electrocardiogram
QRS	QRS Complex
HRV	Heart Rate Variability
MITDB	Mit-Bih Arrhythmia Database
QTDB	Qt Database
NSTDB	Noise Stress Test Database
F1	F1 Score
TP	True Positive
FP	False Positive
FN	False Negative
SDNN	Standard Deviation of Normal-to-Normal Intervals
RMSSD	Root Mean Square of Successive Differences
SNR	Signal-To-Noise Ratio
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error

Appendix A 539

Appendix A.1 540

A.1.1. Literature Gap Analysis for QRS Detection at ≤ 30 Hz 541

To determine if prior work evaluated QRS detection at ≤ 30 Hz, we performed a reproducible citation-based analysis (four stages). 542
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Stage 1 – Seed selection and citation retrieval. 544

Seeds: MIT-BIH database [2] and Pan-Tompkins algorithm [1]. Using Citation Chaser (May 2026, no filters): 4,360 (MIT-BIH) + 7,365 (Pan-Tompkins) records with abstracts. 545
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Stage 2 – LLM coarse screening (per seed). 547

Each CSV was processed separately with openai/gpt-oss-120b (temperature=0.0) to classify: 548
is_qrs_detection, *low_sampling_rate_tested* (≤ 30 Hz), *uses_original_algo*, *is_review_paper*. 549

Output: MIT-BIH QRS = 660, Pan-Tompkins QRS = 1,843 (sum = 2,503 before dedup). Zero papers tested ≤ 30 Hz. 550
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Stage 3 – Expanded keyword funnelling. 552

We applied a broader filter to the combined file to identify QRS detection papers that might be relevant to downsampling or low-rate operation, even if they did not explicitly test ≤ 30 Hz. The filter required: 553
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is_qrs_detection == TRUE 555

is_review_paper != TRUE 556

and at least one of: 557

Explicit *low_sampling_rate_tested* == TRUE (none existed) 558

A numeric sampling rate ≤ 30 Hz found in title, abstract, or notes (e.g., “30 Hz”) 559

A keyword score ≥ 2 from a list including *downsampl*, *resampl*, *decimat*, *compress*, *sparse*, *level crossing*, *compressed sensing*, *wearable*, *low power*, etc.

Result: 850 papers were flagged as “highly relevant” - i.e., QRS detection papers that mention low sampling rates, downsampling, compression, or wearable/low-power contexts.

Stage 4 – Ranking of downsampling/compression experiments.

The 850 candidate papers were scored by a second LLM (deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-V4-Pro, temperature = 0.0) using the prompt in `finalPaperRanking_5.py` (Supplementary material). Each paper received:

A relevance score (0-100, where ≥ 90 requires explicit testing at ≤ 30 Hz).

A category (direct, indirect, background, irrelevant).

A justification and an evidence quote.

The script ran successfully for all 850 papers (170 batches of 5 papers each). The final output (`ranked_gap_analysis.csv`) was analysed.

Other observations:

- Most studies used native rates (250-360 Hz) and never tested downsampling below 100 Hz . [17] [18], [19],[20], [21], [22], [23].
- Compressed-sensing works ([24],[25],[26],[27],[28]) designed new detectors, not standard ones.
- Four major reviews ([29] [30] [31] [32]) mention no evaluation at ≤ 30 Hz (lowest cited = 50 Hz for classification only [32]).

Conclusion: After screening 11,725 raw records \rightarrow 2,503 QRS papers \rightarrow 850 low-rate relevant \rightarrow 28 with experiments \rightarrow 0 systematic evaluations of a standard QRS detector on uniformly downsampled ECG at ≤ 30 Hz. This gap justifies our investigation of intelligent downsampling methods and their performance below 30 Hz.

Table A1. Most relevant studies that reported downsampling performance on QRS detection

Study	Approach	Lowest tested rate	Gap
Zou et al. [11]	Wavelet downsampling + custom detector	60 Hz	Stopped at 60 Hz
Domazet & Gusev [12]	Resampling to 125 Hz + Hamilton detector	125 Hz	No 30 Hz
Ajdaraga & Gusev [13]	Resampling 80-360 Hz, threshold optimisation	80 Hz	Not full detection
Ravanshad et al. [14]	Level-crossing ADC + dedicated detector	avg. 67 Hz (non-uniform)	Non-uniform
Zanoli et al. [15]	Event-based level crossing + modified gQRS	avg. 23 Hz (non-uniform)	Non-uniform, event-driven
Singh et al. [16]	Compressed sensing + RR interval	N/A	No waveform detection

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Appendix A.2

Figure A1, A2 and A3 present the experiment results for MITDB and QTDB.

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Figure A1. QRS detection performance sensitivity and precision for MITDB and QTDB as a function of the target sampling rate. (a) MITDB sensitivity; (b) QTDB sensitivity; (c) MITDB precision; (d) QTDB precision. The native 360/250 Hz baseline (black dashed line) is shown for reference. All four downsampling methods (naïve, max-hold, min-max, adaptive) are compared.

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Figure A2. Heart rate variability errors on the QT Database after downsampling. (a) Mean RR interval error (Δ MeanRR); (b) SDNN error (Δ SDNN); (c) RMSSD error (Δ RMSSD). All values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation relative to the native 250 Hz ground truth. The green shaded area represents the native-rate Pan-Tompkins detector’s own error (mean \pm standard deviation) when compared against ground truth.

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Figure A3. Computational speedup and processing time on the QT Database as a function of the target sampling rate. (a) Speedup (\times native) achieved by processing the downsampled signal; (b) absolute processing time per record (seconds). The native 250 Hz baseline (black dashed line) is shown for reference. Speedup increases as the target rate decreases, reaching approximately $3\times$ at 8 Hz.

References

- [1] J. Pan and W. J. Tompkins, "A Real-Time QRS Detection Algorithm," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. BME-32, no. 3, pp. 230–236, Mar. 1985, doi: 10.1109/TBME.1985.325532.
- [2] G. B. Moody and R. G. Mark, "MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database." physionet.org, 1992. doi: 10.13026/C2F305.
- [3] P. Laguna, R. G. Mark, A. L. Goldberger, and G. B. Moody, "The QT Database." physionet.org, 1997. doi: 10.13026/C24K53.
- [4] H. Sedghamiz, "BioSigKit: A Matlab Toolbox and Interface for Analysis of BioSignals," *J. Open Source Softw.*, vol. 3, no. 30, p. 671, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.21105/joss.00671.
- [5] H. Sedghamiz, "Matlab Implementation of Pan Tompkins ECG QRS detector." Unpublished, 2014. doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14202.59841.
- [6] G. B. Moody, W. Muldrow, and R. G. Mark, "The MIT-BIH Noise Stress Test Database." physionet.org, 1992. doi: 10.13026/C2HS3T.
- [7] H. Akima, "A New Method of Interpolation and Smooth Curve Fitting Based on Local Procedures," *J. ACM*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 589–602, Oct. 1970, doi: 10.1145/321607.321609.
- [8] H. Akima, "A method of bivariate interpolation and smooth surface fitting based on local procedures," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 18–20, Jan. 1974, doi: 10.1145/360767.360779.
- [9] MathWorks, "makima - Modified Akima piecewise cubic Hermite interpolation." Accessed: May 25, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://au.mathworks.com/help/matlab/ref/makima.html>
- [10] J. Malik, E. Z. Soliman, and H.-T. Wu, "An adaptive QRS detection algorithm for ultra-long-term ECG recordings," *J. Electrocardiol.*, vol. 60, pp. 165–171, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jelectrocard.2020.02.016.
- [11] Yao Zou, Jun Han, Xinqian Weng, and Xiaoyang Zeng, "An Ultra-Low Power QRS Complex Detection Algorithm Based on Down-Sampling Wavelet Transform," *IEEE Signal Process. Lett.*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 515–518, May 2013, doi: 10.1109/LSP.2013.2254475.
- [12] E. Domazet and M. Gusev, "Improving the QRS detection for one-channel ECG sensor," *Technol. Health Care*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 623–642, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.3233/THC-181589.
- [13] E. Ajaraga and M. Gusev, "Analysis of sampling frequency and resolution in ECG signals," in *2017 25th Telecommunication Forum (TELFOR)*, Belgrade: IEEE, Nov. 2017, pp. 1–4. doi: 10.1109/TELFOR.2017.8249438.
- [14] N. Ravanshad, H. Rezaee-Dehsorkh, R. Lotfi, and Yong Lian, "A Level-Crossing Based QRS-Detection Algorithm for Wearable ECG Sensors," *IEEE J. Biomed. Health Inform.*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 183–192, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2013.2274809.
- [15] S. Zanolli, T. Teijeiro, F. Montagna, and D. Atienza, "An Event-Based System for Low-Power ECG QRS Complex Detection," in *2020 Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE)*, Grenoble, France: IEEE, Mar. 2020, pp. 258–263. doi: 10.23919/DATE48585.2020.9116498.
- [16] H. Singh, M. S. Manikandan, and R. B. Pachori, "Compressed ECG Sensing Based RR Interval Measurement for Fast Entropy Analysis of Heart Rate Variability," in *2023 9th International Conference on Signal Processing and Communication (ICSC)*, NOIDA, India: IEEE, Dec. 2023, pp. 516–521. doi: 10.1109/ICSC60394.2023.10441299.
- [17] A. Burguera, "Fast QRS Detection and ECG Compression Based on Signal Structural Analysis," *IEEE J. Biomed. Health Inform.*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 123–131, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2018.2792404.
- [18] J. Li, A. Ashraf, B. Cardiff, R. C. Panicker, Y. Lian, and D. John, "Low Power Optimisations for IoT Wearable Sensors Based on Evaluation of Nine QRS Detection Algorithms," *IEEE Open J. Circuits Syst.*, vol. 1, pp. 115–123, 2020, doi: 10.1109/OJCS.2020.3009822.
- [19] Xiao Tan *et al.*, "EMD-Based Electrocardiogram Delineation for a Wearable Low-Power ECG Monitoring Device," *Can. J. Electr. Comput. Eng.*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 212–221, 2014, doi: 10.1109/CJECE.2014.2316852.
- [20] A. Kumar, M. Kumar, and R. Komaragiri, "Design of a Biorthogonal Wavelet Transform Based R-Peak Detection and Data Compression Scheme for Implantable Cardiac Pacemaker Systems," *J. Med. Syst.*, vol. 42, no. 6, p. 102, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s10916-018-0953-2.

- [21] B. Zhang, L. Sieler, Y. Morère, B. Bolmont, and G. Bourhis, "A Modified Algorithm for QRS Complex Detection for FPGA Implementation," *Circuits Syst. Signal Process.*, vol. 37, no. 7, pp. 3070–3092, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s00034-017-0711-6. 635
636
- [22] S. Lee, Y. Jeong, J. Kwak, D. Park, and K. H. Park, "Advanced Real-Time Dynamic Programming in the Polygonal Approximation of ECG Signals for a Lightweight Embedded Device," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 162850–162861, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2952399. 637
638
639
- [23] C. Hernando-Ramiro, L. Lovisolo, F. Cruz-Roldán, and M. Blanco-Velasco, "Matching Pursuit Decomposition on Electrocardiograms for Joint Compression and QRS Detection," *Circuits Syst. Signal Process.*, vol. 38, no. 6, pp. 2653–2676, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s00034-018-0986-2. 640
641
642
- [24] J. K. Pant and S. Krishnan, "Robust QRS detection for HRV estimation from compressively sensed ECG measurements for remote health-monitoring systems," *Physiol. Meas.*, vol. 39, no. 3, p. 035002, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1088/1361-6579/aaa3c9. 643
644
- [25] G. Da Poian, C. Liu, R. Bernardini, R. Rinaldo, and G. D. Clifford, "Atrial fibrillation detection on compressed sensed ECG," *Physiol. Meas.*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 1405–1425, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1088/1361-6579/aa7652. 645
646
- [26] A. Galli, C. Narduzzi, and G. Giorgi, "ECG Monitoring and Anomaly Detection Based on Compressed Measurements," in *Proceedings of the 2018 3rd International Conference on Biomedical Imaging, Signal Processing*, Bari Italy: ACM, Oct. 2018, pp. 10–17. doi: 10.1145/3288200.3288206. 647
648
649
- [27] D. Mitra and S. Rajan, "Deterministic Compressed Domain Analysis of Multi-channel ECG Measurements," in *2020 IEEE International Symposium on Medical Measurements and Applications (MeMeA)*, Bari, Italy: IEEE, Jun. 2020, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/MeMeA49120.2020.9137252. 650
651
652
- [28] G. Laudato *et al.*, "Identification of R-peak occurrences in compressed ECG signals," in *2020 IEEE International Symposium on Medical Measurements and Applications (MeMeA)*, Bari, Italy: IEEE, Jun. 2020, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/MeMeA49120.2020.9137207. 653
654
- [29] S. R. Raj Kailash Chandra; Shankar, Om, "Development of robust, fast and efficient QRS complex detector: a methodological review," *Australas. Phys. Eng. Sci. Med.*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 581–600, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s13246-018-0670-7. 655
656
- [30] A. Jaya Prakash, A. Nasreddine Belkacem, I. M. Elfadel, H. F. Jelinek, and M. Atef, "Advances in machine and deep learning for ECG beat classification: a systematic review," *Front. Digit. Health*, vol. 7, p. 1649923, Nov. 2025, doi: 10.3389/fdgth.2025.1649923. 657
658
- [31] Z. Zhou, Y. Wang, X. Cheng, and J. Wang, "Evolution of Heart Rate Variability (HRV) Analysis Methodologies (2000–2025): From Task Force Standards to Wearables, AI, and Clinical Translation," *Biomed. Signal Process. Control*, vol. 123, p. 110575, Sep. 2026, doi: 10.1016/j.bspc.2026.110575. 659
660
661
- [32] A. Salimi, S. V. Kalmady, A. Hindle, O. Zaiane, and P. Kaul, "Exploring Best Practices for ECG Pre-Processing in Machine Learning," 2023, *arXiv*. doi: 10.48550/ARXIV.2311.04229. 662
663
664